

ACTIVITY OF THE ULUGBEK OBSERVATORY DURING THE RENAISSANCE OF THE TIMURID ERA

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Annotasiya. Temuriylar davrida Samarqand ilm-ma'rifat rivojlangan maskanlardan biri edi. Amir Temur va Mirzo Ulug'bek ilm-fan homiysiga aylanadi. Mamlakatda islom qoidalariga asoslangan, xalqparvar va adolatli siyosat yuritiladi. Mirzo Ulug'bek davrida yirik Rasadxona quriladi va u G'arb mamlakatlarida Samarqand Akademiyasi nomi bilan mashhur bo'ladi. Temuriylar davri Renessasining muhim ilmiy maktablaridan biri edi, u haqiqiy Akademiya edi. Ammo bu maskan juda qisqa muddatda faoliyat yuritdi. Mamlakatdagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy beqarorlik natijasida bu akademiya tanazzulga yuz tutdi. Ushu tezisda Ulug'bek tomonidan asos solingan Rasadxona faoliyati va uning tanazuli ilmiy asosda qisqacha tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: rasadxona, Renessans, Ziji jadidi ko'ragoniy, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Samarqand, astronomiya, matematika, yulduzlar, sekstant.

Abstract. During the Timurid era, Samarkand emerged as a hub of knowledge and enlightenment. Amir Timur and Mirzo Ulug'bek supported scientific endeavors and implemented fair and people-friendly policies based on Islamic principles. Under Mirzo Ulugbek's rule, a significant observatory was constructed in Samarkand, known as the Samarkand Academy in the West. It played a crucial role in the Timurid Renaissance as a prominent scientific institution. However, due to socio-political turmoil in the region, the academy's operations were short-lived and it eventually declined. This thesis examines the establishment and subsequent downfall of Ulugbek's observatory from a scientific perspective.

Key words: observatory, Renaissance, Ziji Jadidi Koragoniy, Mirzo Ulugbek, Samarkand, astronomy, mathematics, stars, sextant.

Аннотация. В эпоху Тимуридов Самарканд превратился в центр знаний и просвещения. Амир Тимур и Мирзо Улугбек поддерживали научные начинания и проводили справедливую и доброжелательную к людям политику, основанную на исламских принципах. При Мирзо Улугбеке в Самарканде была построена крупная обсерватория, известная на Западе как Самаркандская академия. Он сыграл решающую роль в эпоху Тимуридов как выдающееся научное учреждение. Однако из-за социально-политических потрясений в регионе деятельность академии была недолгой и в конечном итоге пришла в упадок. В данной диссертации с научной точки зрения рассматривается создание и последующее падение обсерватории Улугбека.

Ключевые слова: обсерватория, Ренессанс, Зиджи Джадиди Корагоний, Мирзо Улугбек, Самарканд, астрономия, математика, звезды, секстант.

INTRODUCTION

For centuries, Samarkand has been the center of attention of scientists from all over the world. Many scientists and tourists from different countries visited the city and wrote about it in their memories. The convenient geographical location of the city made it important as an intermediary and leading city in the Silk Road trade.

In 1370, Samarkand became the capital of Amir Temur's empire. The great commander paid great attention to the development of the city. According to his orders, a new city was built on a natural hill in 1371-1372 south of Afrosiab. According to the owner Amir Temur, Samarkand should have remained the most fertile and fortified city in the world. The outskirts of the city are surrounded by a strong and high defensive wall. The wall was 8 meters high and over 3 meters wide at the bottom, and the outer perimeter was fortified by a wide and deep moat. This place was called "Hisar", and the Ark was built on a natural hill in its western part. The area where the arch is located was more than 34 hectares. Government offices, mosques and madrasahs, royal residences, a huge library with 15,000 volumes of rare books, Amir Temur's treasury and throne, mint, armory workshops, baths, pool, dungeon and other buildings are located in the Arch. The culture of the city also developed during the reigns of Amir Temur's successors, Shahrukh, Ulugbek, and Sultan Husayn Boykara. In particular, a peaceful way of life continued in Samarkand during the reign of Mirzo Ulugbek. Samarkand developed as a center of science and trade, became a place where mature scientists of the Eastern world gathered, and this period entered history under the name of the Renaissance of the Timurid era. This article analyzes the Samarkand academy or Ulugbek observatory founded by Mirzo Ulugbek in Samarkand based on scientific sources.

Renaissance period

For the first time, the term Renaissance was mentioned in Europe in the 15th-16th centuries, and it was believed that this period first appeared in Europe. But in 1909, Austrian orientalist Adam Mes published a work entitled "The Muslim Renaissance".¹ In his work, he proved that the Renaissance actually originated in the East. Similarly, the Russian orientalist N.N. Konrad proves that the Renaissance² began in China in the 7th -8th centuries and later spread to India and Central Asian countries, particularly during the Timurid period.

The first Renaissance began in our country between the 9th and 12th centuries. By the 13th century, it was in decline due to the Mongol invasion. During the reign of the Timurids in the 14th -15th centuries, the second stage of the Renaissance developed. Science reached its peak during the Timurid period. No matter where Amir Temur went, he brought scientists, artisans, artists from that country to Samarkand. He patronized science

Special importance is attached to the development of construction, pottery, blacksmithing, jewelry, weaving and paper production. For example, the "sultani", "Samarkand Sultanate" "clean and white", "ordinary" papers of Samarkand artisans were very popular.³

The city of Samarkand became one of the most beautiful and prosperous cities in Asia during the time of Amir Temur and the Timurids. In the 14th -15th centuries, Amir Temur and the Timurids, in particular Shahrukh, Ulug'bek, Husayn Boyqaro⁴, Movarounnahr and Khurasan, the ideological freedom and attention to culture within the framework of Islam led to the development of science, literature, and art. This was important in the emergence of a new Renaissance period during the Timurid period.

Science in Samarkand during the time of Mirzo Ulugbek

¹ A.F.Isroilov <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sharq-renessansi-davrida-ilm-fan-va-madaniyat-rivoji/viewer>

² R.K.Ganiyeva Vostochniy Renessans I yego traditsii v tyurkskix literaturax: avtoreferat dis. ... doktora filologicheskix nauk: 10.01.03.- Kazan, 1992.-38s.:il.

³ Мукминова Р.Г. Очерки истории ремесла в Самарканде и в Бухаре. XVI в. – Т., 1976. – С. 95-103.

⁴ M.D.Pardaeva The Heritage Of Our Great Ancestors And The Third Renessans/ The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. July30, 2021| P.41., <https://theamericanjournals.com/index.php/tajssei/article/view/243/224>

After the death of Amir Temur in 1405, in 1409, Mirza Ulugbek sat on the throne of Samarkand. He ruled the country for 40 years (1409-1449). During his time, science flourished in Samarkand. In Samarkand, he built bazaars, caravanserais, tim, charsu, baths, madrasas, mosques, and a scientific observatory. He paid special attention to science. He built a madrasa in Samarkand in 1417-1420. It should be said that initially analytical and practical work on astronomy and mathematics was carried out in this madrasa. During Ulugbek's time, he built various green corners and ponds for the purpose of greening the city. So, among the buildings built by his grandfather, he also built many beautiful buildings. During his time, valuable books were written on philosophy, philosophy of speech and philosophy of religion. Inscriptions written in the Persian-Tajik language with the rare art of calligraphy, verses and hadiths from books written in Arabic decorate the arches and facades of the buildings built by the Timurids.⁵ During this period (in 1417), the total number of scholars from different cities of Movarunnahr and Khurasan in Samarkand exceeded 100. In particular, there were writers, historians, poets, painters, and geographers among the scientists. But the position of scientists in the field of astronomy and mathematics was much higher.⁶

Ulugbek Observatory. In 1424-1429, the largest observatory of its time was built in Samarkand by Mirzo Ulugbek. In Europe, this observatory became known as "Samarkand Academy". This observatory was built on the hill of Kohak (now Cho'ponota) on the banks of the Obi Rahmat stream. According to experts, the height of the observatory was 30.4 meters, the diameter of the circle was 46.2 meters. The radius of the main part of the building was a 40.2 meter observation instrument called a sextant.⁷ Mirzo Ulug'bek directly participated in the design and construction of the observatory. In addition to government work, once a week he gave lectures on astronomy or mathematics at the observatory.

It is difficult to give a clear conclusion about what the observatory was like in its time. Because this building was completely destroyed by the 17th century. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur wrote in his "Boburnoma" that the Ulugbek Observatory was in a very dilapidated and neglected state⁸. By 1908, the Russian scientist V. L. Vyatkin, based on the analysis of historical documents, determined its location and studied it. In addition, in 1941, M.E. Masson, and in 1948, V.A. Shishkin conducted archaeological excavations. Based on the conducted research, scientists found out that the observatory was a very luxurious building in the form of a cylinder, 3 floors, built with baked bricks. The surface of the observatory building is decorated with tiles and secret rivets. These opinions are also confirmed by the information given in Boburnama. In the rooms of the observatory, Ulugbek drew the important achievements of the scientists before him in the field of catastrophes with various shapes, images, numbers, and patterns.⁹ There was also a library in the observatory. An image of the sky, a map of the stars, a globe with mountains, seas, and countries are made on the inner wall. In the observatory there were small instruments: armillary sphere, 2, 4 and 7 ring gauges, triangula, sun and star clocks, astrolabe and others. According to Associate Professor J. Qayumov, the observatory had the following devices:

- Zat-al-halak-armillali sphere (ring), consisting of several rings describing the circles in the celestial sphere, with the help of rings it is possible to observe the planets.

⁵ R.Xodizoda Samarqandnoma "Tafakkur" T., 2011. 41-bet

⁶ A.Axmedov Ulug'bek Muhammad Tarag'ay T., 2011. 31-bet

⁷ A.S.Uralov, L.A.Raximov Temuriylar arxitekturasi tarixi. SamDU., Samarqand, 2020. 68-bet

⁸ Z.M.Bobur Boburnoma T., 2018.

⁹ A.S.Uralov, L.A.Raximov Temuriylar arxitekturasi tarixi. SamDU., Samarqand, 2020. 99-bet

- Zat-al-shubatayn - triquetra (triangular), an ancient aeronomic instrument consisting of two branches.
- Zat-as-suk-batainy - diopter.
- Shamila is an example of a universal instrument used instead of an astrolabe and a square.
- Ruhama - a marble slab - Sundial.
- Scale (gnomon) is a measuring device.
- Kura falakiya - sky globe.¹⁰

The Sun, Moon, planets and individual stars were observed with the help of this scientific equipment. The largest astronomical work of Mirzo Ulugbek "Zizhi Jadidi Koragoniy" was created in the observatory. At the observatory, scientists such as Giyosiddin Koshi, Qazizoda Rumi, Ali Kushchi were among Ulugbek's closest advisers. Ustad Ismail, Maulana Ibrahim, Maulana Badriddin and other scientists gave their lectures at the observatory. Today, only the entrance to the observatory and the 11-meter underground part of the sextant have been preserved. According to historical sources, the bricks of the Observatory, which were demolished between 1588 and 1598¹¹ or more precisely, between 1590 and 1592, were used for other constructions.

Turmoil and instability in the socio-political life of the country in the 15th century had negative consequences for the scientist Mirzo Ulug'bek, who was studying the science of catastrophes and mathematics. The conflict between father and son ended with the murder of Mirzo Ulugbek. After Ulugbek's death, Samarkand scientists dispersed to the countries of the Near and Middle East. In particular, Ulugbek's student Ali Kushchi went to Istanbul in 1473 and built an observatory there.

Mirzo Ulugbek was often engaged in state affairs and wrote 4 works during his life. These are: "Zizhi jadidi Ko'ragoniy", "Treatise on determining the sine of one degree", "Risolai Ulug'bek", "Tarihi Arba' ulus" (History of four nations). Currently, there are about 120 Persian and more than 15 Arabic copies of "Ziji Jadidi Ko'ragoniy".¹² In addition, this work has been translated into English, French, Latin, Urdu, Russian and other languages. The work contains 1018 star movements. The first section of the introduction is devoted to dates, the second to practical astronomy, the third to the idea of planetary motion, and the fourth to the field of astrology¹³.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the Ulugbek observatory was a real Samarkand academy founded during the Timurid period. The scientific works created here were considered an important driver in the European Renaissance, in particular, in the development of the European School of Astronomy. In the renaissance of the Timurid period, the role of the conditions made by the state was incomparable in the development of such science. After all, Mirzo Ulug'bek was not only the ruler of the country, but also a great astronomer and scientist. The scientific works created by the scientist have a special place in the development of world civilization. In particular, the work "Zizhi jadidi Ko'ragoniy" was of great service in creating their own astronomical tables of other nations. According to historical sources, when Ali Kushchi took "Ziji Jadidi Koragoni" to

¹⁰ J.Qayumov Ulug'bek rasadxonasida qanday jihozlardan foydalanilgan?/ <https://zarnews.uz/uz/post/ul-ras> 06.10.2019

¹¹ Ismoil Bekjon. Ulug'bek Rasadxonasini kim buzgan? <https://www.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/maqolalar/ismoil-bekjon-ulug-bek-rasadxonasini-kim-buzdirgan> 30.10. 2013

¹² A.Axmedov Ulug'bek Muhammad Tarag'ay T., 2011. 34-bet

¹³ A.Arapov Samarqand (Markaziy Osiyo durdonalari) T., 2019. 70-bet

Istanbul, he did not have any knowledge about it in the Ottoman Empire. Unfortunately, such a huge scientific academy, built in the Middle Ages, was condemned by local officials and religious scholars, and the scientist's scientific views were not supported, and eventually tragically declined.

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